

Total Alkaloid Content and β -hematin Inhibitory Potential of a Hepta-herbal *Agbo-iba* Antimalarial Decoction

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Abstract

Malaria, one of the deadliest diseases in the world is most prevalent in tropical and sub-tropical regions where medicinal plants are frequently used for its management. Given that medicinal plants play a significant role in the treatment of malaria, mechanistic studies are needed in order to validate their efficacy as well as for their optimization. In the current study, the total alkaloid in a hepta-herbal *Agbo-iba* (HHA) extract used as traditional decoction for managing malaria in Benin City, Nigeria was quantified. Furthermore, its ability to inhibit β -hematin formation was conducted *in vitro*. The alkaloidal content and β -hematin inhibitory potential of *Annickia affinis*; one of HHA's constituent plants was also investigated alongside. HHA with a β -hematin inhibitory potential of $IC_{50} = 88 \mu\text{g/ml}$, possessed an alkaloidal content of 5.9 %w/w whereas, *A. affinis* decoction inhibited β -hematin formation by $IC_{50} = 60 \mu\text{g/ml}$ and possessed an alkaloidal content of 81 %w/w. *A. affinis* with an ~ 14 -fold higher alkaloidal content is thus only ~ 1.5 -fold better at inhibiting β -hematin formation than HHA. These results suggest that other plants aside from *A. affinis* may be contributing to HHA's β -hematin inhibitory ability. Future mechanistic studies should investigate all HHA's constituent plants alongside the hepta-herbal so as to reveal their contributions.

Keywords: Alkaloids, β -hematin, Hepta-herbal *Agbo-iba*, Synergy, Malaria

1.0. Introductions

The malaria parasite is increasingly wreaking havoc to developing nations of the world with Nigeria having to shoulder the largest share of the global burden of the disease [1]. For ages, plants have been exploited by mankind for their pharmacological benefits. Often times some of these plants are combined with others to achieve the desired effect [2]. *Agbo-iba*, which translates to medicine for fever in Yoruba language (one of Nigeria's three most spoken languages) happens to be one of such plant mixtures. *Agbo-iba* is useful for the management of malaria mostly in the western part of Nigeria [3]. Given that up to 80% of individuals in developing countries rely on medicinal plants as a primary source of healthcare [4], it is imperative that scientific assessment of plants with ethnomedicinal claims

of benefit be done. Further, their bioactive principles and target (s) need to also be determined so as to guide their standardization and rational use.

Recently, the hepta-herbal *Agbo-iba* dubbed HHA was evaluated for safety and efficacy [3]. One of its plant components, *Annickia affinis* was reported to contribute immensely to the antiplasmodial activity of the herbal mixture having 34-fold better antiplasmodial activity than the herbal combo [3]. Alkaloids of the protoberberine class are responsible for the antiplasmodial activity of *A. affinis* as well as *A. chlorantha* (a closely related species) [3,5]. The presence of these compounds was confirmed in HHA using both thin layer chromatography (TLC) and liquid chromatography mass spectrometry (LCMS) metabolite fingerprinting

[3], following which they were isolated and purified [6].

Malaria parasite resistance to existing drugs has necessitated the search for new drugs. One of the strategies to slow down malaria parasite resistance development is to partner antimalarial drugs targeting different parasite pathways [7,8]. This places a need for the identification of drug targets [9]. Target-based drug discovery has revolutionized antimalarial research by enabling the identification of essential parasite proteins for rational drug design and high-throughput screening [10,11,12]. These approaches have not only reduced cost but also, the time for antimalarial drug discovery [9, 13]. This shift in antimalarial drug discovery from phenotypic screening [9] toward target-based approaches has seen the prioritization of targets expressed in particular parasite stages [14, 15] as well as targets which are expressed in multiple parasite stages [9, 16, 17]. These have resulted in the identification of medicinal plants as well as a number of compounds possessing multistage antiplasmodial activity [18, 19, 20, 21, 22].

Despite *Plasmodium falciparum* evolving to become resistant to chloroquine by generating mutations to the chloroquine resistance transporter [23], hemozoin inhibition is still an important target today as drugs targeting this pathway and do not share cross resistance with chloroquine are still being sort after [24, 25]. The present study thus set out to quantify the total alkaloid content in HHA and *A. affinis* as well as explore their β -hematin inhibitory potential as a possible mechanism for the antiplasmodial action of HHA.

2.0. Materials and Methods

2.1. Materials

Hemin chloride and chloroquine diphosphate were obtained from Sigma, USA. Bromocresol green, Tween 20, HPLC grade methanol and chloroform were obtained from Merck. Berberine chloride was obtained from Sigma, India. All other reagents and chemicals used for this study were of analytical grade.

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Sample collection and preparation

Plant parts of the heptal-herbal were collected from their natural habitats. Authentication was done in the Department of Plant Biology and

Biotechnology, University of Benin, Nigeria. Voucher specimens were deposited in the herbarium of the same department. The Voucher specimen numbers of the seven plants that comprise the herbal mixture are as follows, *Alstonia boonei* (UBH- A343), *Annickia affinis* (UBH-A511), *Anthocleista djalensis* (UBH-A428), *Azadirachta indica* (UBH-A286), *Cymbopogon citratus* (UBH-C451), *Nauclea pobeguunii* (UBH-N180) and *Sorghum bicolor* (UBH-S468). Their names were thereafter checked in October, 2022 using <http://www.theplantlist.org>. Following this, the decoction of the herbal mixture was prepared as previously described [3]. Seven grams (7 g) each of the HHA plant components were weighed and placed in a beaker. To this, 1 L of distilled water was added. Sample was decocted for 1 hr at 100°C, after which it was cooled, filtered, freeze dried, and kept at 4°C until time of use. *A. affinis* decoction was prepared in a similar way as HHA.

2.2.2. Determination of total alkaloid content

Alkaloids were quantified using the colorimetry method as described by [26] with minor modifications. Firstly, a standard calibration curve was prepared following which the alkaloid content of samples was estimated by extrapolation. The procedure of some of the reagents used for this study are given below.

Preparation of Bromocresol green mixture (10^{-4} M)

Bromocresol green (10^{-4} M) was prepared by adding 69.8 mg of bromocresol green and 3 ml of NaOH to 100 ml of distilled water in a beaker. The mixture was warmed and stirred until it completely dissolved. Thereafter, the volume was made up to 1000 ml with distilled water.

Preparation of phosphate buffer (pH 4.7)

Phosphate buffer (pH 4.7) was prepared by adding 0.2 M citric acid (42.02 g citric acid in 1 L distilled water) to 2M sodium phosphate (71.6g NaHPO_4 in 1L distilled water) and adjusting the pH to 4.7 by adding few drops of 2M NaOH.

2.5.1. Preparation of standard calibration curve

To quantify the alkaloidal content of HHA and *A. affinis* decoction, a standard calibration curve was first plotted. To do this, 500 μg berberine standard was prepared in 1 ml of 1% H_2SO_4 in distilled

water. From this, aliquots (0.2, 0.6, 0.8 and 1.0) were transferred into separatory funnels and made up to 1 ml with 1% H₂SO₄ in distilled water. Thereafter, 5 ml of phosphate buffer (pH 4.7) and 5 ml of bromocresol green (70 mg /L) were added. Chloroform (5 ml x 2) was then added, followed by thorough shaking. Thereafter, the chloroform layer containing the complex was retrieved, diluted with 10 ml chloroform and absorbance read at 415 nm against blank (which was prepared as above but without berberine). After this, a standard calibration curve of absorbance against amount of berberine in mg was plotted. The standard calibration curve was checked for precision by repeating the experiment thrice using the same quantity of berberine. The accuracy of the method was determined by calculating the %recovery following the addition of 1 mg berberine to *Cymbopogon citratus* leaf decoction (Table 1) (one of HHA's constituent

plants) for which alkaloid was previously not detected [3].

2.5.2. Quantification of alkaloid in HHA and *A. affinis*

A. affinis or HHA (10 mg) were dissolved in 1 ml of 1% H₂SO₄ in distilled water. To test samples in separatory funnels, 5 ml of phosphate buffer (pH 4.7) and 5 ml of bromocresol green (70 mg /L) were added. Thereafter, 5 ml of chloroform to which the precipitated alkaloids partitioned into was added. The chloroform layer was then collected in a test tube. Extraction was repeated with another 5 ml chloroform which was added to the previous chloroform layer collected (Figure 1). Following this, absorbance was read on a spectrophotometer (Thechmel and Thechmel 20D, USA) at 415 nm. Absorbance was extrapolated from berberine standard calibration curve. Thus, alkaloidal content was expressed as %w/w.

Figure 1: Procedure for the quantitative determination of alkaloids in HHA and *A. affinis*.

Samples (10 mg) were dissolved in 1 ml of 1% H₂SO₄ after which 5 ml of phosphate buffer was added (1). Thereafter, 5 ml of bromocresol green was added resulting in the formation of a yellow-orange complex (2). This was followed by addition of 5 ml x 2 of chloroform (3) and vigorous shaking such that the alkaloid-bromocresol complex formed partitioned into the chloroform phase (lower layer) (4) that was retrieved in a test tube and absorbance read at 415 nm. Experiment was done in triplicate for both samples.

2.6. *In vitro* β -hematin inhibition assay

This was done using the method described by [27]. Hemin chloride (250 μ L, 0.5 mg/mL) was prepared in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) on the day the assay was conducted. Thereafter, 0.5M acetate buffer (500 μ L; pH 4.4) was added in triplicate Eppendorf tubes following which 250 μ L of test samples (HHA and *A. affinis* and decoction) were added at concentrations of 0 – 250 and 0 – 100 μ g/ml, respectively. Water was added in place of samples for negative control. This method was validated by using chloroquine; a standard antimalarial drug which is capable of inhibiting hemozoin formation [24,25]. Samples were thereafter incubated for 24 hr at room temperature and centrifuged for 10 min at 4000 rpm. Unreacted hemin was removed following centrifugal wash with 1000 μ l DMSO.

Afterwards, the β -hematin formed in each tube were dissolved using 1000 μ L of 0.1 M NaOH and the absorbance measured at 405 nm with the aid of a spectrophotometer. Percentage inhibition was calculated using the formula below while IC₅₀ was computed using dose-response curves.

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = 100 \times \{1 - (\text{Absorbance of sample} / \text{Absorbance of control})\}.$$

3.0. Results

3.1. Total alkaloid content of *A. affinis* and HHA

The standard calibration curve for berberine is given in Figure 2. The curve was linear from 0 to 1.0 mg. The linearity range and the other parameters assessed (Table 1) confirmed validity of the plot [26].

Figure 2: Standard calibration curve for berberine. Curve was linear from 0 to 1.0 mg

Table 1: Validation Parameters for Quantitative Determination of Alkaloid in Samples

Parameter	Score
Linearity range (mg/ml)	0 – 1.0
Correlation	0.9296
% Recovery	95.20 ± 4.76

While HHA possessed an alkaloidal content of 5.9 % w/w, *A. affinis* decoction had 81.10% w/w i.e. ~14-fold higher alkaloidal content than HHA (Table 2).

Table 2: Total alkaloid content of HHA and *A. affinis* decoction

	Total alkaloid content %w/w
<i>A. affinis</i>	81.10 ± 1.06 ^a
HHA	5.90 ± 0.69 ^b

Different lowercase letters denote significant difference (P < 0.05) between samples

3.2. Assessment of the β-hematin inhibitory potential of HHA and *A. affinis*

Despite possessing ~14-fold higher alkaloidal content than HHA, *A. affinis* decoction was only ~1.5-fold better at inhibiting heme complexation than the hepta-herbal extract (Table 3; Figure 3).

Table 3: β-hematin inhibitory potential of HHA and *A. affinis*

	IC ₅₀ inhibition of heme complexation (µg/ml)
<i>A. affinis</i>	60.00 ± 6.92 ^a
HHA	88.31 ± 0.01 ^b
CQ (µM)	17 ± 1.21

Different lowercase letters denote significant difference (P < 0.05) between samples. Key: CQ = Chloroquine

Figure 3: β-hematin inhibitory potential of decoctions of HHA (a), *A. affinis* (b) and chloroquine (c)

4.0. Discussion

A hepta-herbal, locally referred to as *Agbo-iba* and used for managing malaria in Benin City, Nigeria, was recently reported to be potent against malaria parasites *in vitro* due to quaternary protoberberine alkaloids contributed by *A. affinis*; one of its constituent plants [3]. Also, qualitative screening of phytochemicals revealed the presence of alkaloids in HHA and some of its constituent plants at varied detection levels viz: *A. boonei*, *N. pobeguinii*, *S. bicolor* and *A. affinis* [3]. Except for *A. affinis*, for which high levels of alkaloids were detected, low levels of alkaloids were recorded for HHA and three of its other constituent plants [3]. As alkaloids are known to be responsible for the antiplasmodial activity of *A. affinis* [3,5]; a major contributor to HHA's antiplasmodial activity [3], its total alkaloid content as well as that of HHA were quantified in the present study. From available literature, this is the first study to quantify the total alkaloid content of decoctions of HHA and *A. affinis*. Their inhibition of heme complexation is also reported here for the first time.

During its intraerythrocytic developmental cycle stage which lasts 48 hrs, the malaria parasite ingests host's hemoglobin for growth. This it degrades in its acidic food vacuole. During this process, heme is released. To avert toxicity from heme, the parasite complexes heme monomers forming what is known as hemozoin or malaria pigment [28]. Many compounds with antiplasmodial activity including chloroquine [29], artemisinin [30] and quercetin [31] have been reported to inhibit this heme complexation process by forming heme adducts. Given that *Plasmodium falciparum* has since generated resistant mutations that compromise chloroquine's antimalarial action [32], agents with similar hemozoin inhibitory ability as chloroquine and can kill chloroquine resistant parasites will be highly valuable for antimalarial drug discovery and development [24,25]. The present study thus compared the ability of decoctions of HHA and *A. affinis* to inhibit heme complexation *in vitro*. Both samples were found to possess IC₅₀ values of 60 (*A. affinis*) and 88 (HHA) µg/ml respectively for inhibition of β-hematin formation. From literature, scoring of β-hematin inhibition has only been done for pure compounds [33]. Extracts are typically compared against one another [34,35]. For pure compounds, potency is often measured relative to chloroquine standard [33]. Compounds having IC₅₀ ≤110 µM for

inhibiting β-hematin formation are considered hits [33]. A dose of 110 µM of chloroquine diphosphate translates to ~60 µg/ml. Thus, with IC₅₀ values of 60 and 88 µg/ml, *A. affinis* and HHA are highly potent inhibitors of β-hematin formation from where hits may be isolated.

A. affinis decoction which was previously reported to possess an ~34-fold better ability of inhibiting malaria parasite (IC₅₀*Pf3D7*) growth than HHA [3] was observed in this study to possess an ~14-fold higher alkaloid content but only an ~1.5-fold better ability to inhibit β-hematin formation than HHA (Figure 3). This finding thus suggests that aside from *A. affinis* whose concentration is seven times less in HHA, other HHA constituent plants may also be contributing to the hepta-herbal formula's β-hematin inhibitory property. From previous report [3], *A. affinis* is more potent than HHA *in vitro* but not *in vivo*. This, highlights the possibility of missing out on desirable interactions such as synergy and additivity that can result in additional therapeutic benefit when herbs are used in combination [36].

5.0. Conclusion

This study suggests that the hepta-herbal *Agbo-iba* decoction used for managing malaria in Benin City, Nigeria, kills the malaria parasite in part by inhibiting heme complexation. Furthermore, aside from *A. affinis*, other plant constituent(s) of the hepta-herbal combo are likely contributing to parasite killing via inhibition of hemozoin formation.

6.0. Recommendation

Future mechanistic studies directed at identifying the inhibitors of heme complexation by HHA or exploring other malaria parasite targets should thus take into consideration the possibility of synergy or additivity amongst the hepta-herbal extract's constituent plants.

7.0. Conflict of Interest

None declared

8.0. References

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